

Annotation. In this article, dialogue and the role of nonverbal means in dialogue is discussed. Speech activity of a person is valid in three ways: speaking, reading and listening. Speaking means that the speaker gives information, advises, orders, and asks about unknown things. When speaking, the speaker's knowledge, culture, morals and manners come to the fore. Dialogue is one of the forms of speech in which every thought is directed directly to the interlocutor. The role of nonverbal means in dialogic speech is crucial and they are considered to be important and impressive part of the communication.

Key words: nonverbal means, dialogue, kinesics, skin reaction, communication, discussion, dialogic text.

The syntactic structure of dialogic speech is simpler than that of monologic speech. Dialogue is distinguished by the brevity of thoughts. It contains only the most necessary things to continue the conversation and does not explain the events in detail, and also consists of question-and-answer, discussion, various actions and exchange of ideas[11]. In this respect, the dialogue is not like a monologue:

The etymology of any word helps to understand its deep meaning. The word dialogue comes from the Greek word "dialogos", which means "logos" - "word" and "dia" - "through"[12]. Dialogue can be not only between two people, but also between any number of people. So, a dialogue is a written or spoken exchange of ideas between two or more people. In dialogue, no one tries to win, on the contrary, everyone is the same winner.

Dialogue is a process of exchange of ideas. The linguist A. Shomaqsudov stated the following about the dialogue: "...a dialogic text is a whole speech unit consisting of a set of sentences of two persons that form a thematic and logical whole, one of which complements, defines and explains the other."[10;37]

Dialogue is widespread in ancient literature and used in the works of Greek philosophers and writers such as Cicero, Sineica, Reutarchus, Tacitus, Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle[9;12]. In particular, Socrates conducted many studies on dialogue and revealed its main features. It can also be seen in the studies of M.Buber[1;20], D.Bohm[2], M.Bakhtin[4], D.Nikulin[3], U.Lafasov[5], D.Babayeva[6], F.Karimova[7] in world and Uzbek linguistics.

In the process of dialogue, people exchange ideas with each other and get various information. Accordingly, Buber emphasized that dialogue can consist not only of words, but also of silence and various actions (gestures). Gestures, facial expressions, body movements, various voice states - additional tools involved in communication fulfill the tasks of filling and clarifying the content of communication[1;20]. A person expresses information briefly and succinctly in a live conversational speech, actively uses verbal and non-verbal means to increase the emotionality and impact of the thought.

When people communicate with each other, in the process of conveying certain information to the listener, hand, head, shoulder, body, facial movements, high-low voice, long-shortness, halting pronunciation of words is distinguished by its uniqueness. Non-verbal communication shows characteristics such as behavior, vocal characteristics, appearance and

behavior of the speaker[8]. Non-verbal communication is defined as communication without words. Everything, including material objects, physical space, and time systems. Even if verbal speech is not used, it is impossible not to use non-verbal communication, even silence speaks.

At this point, the non-verbal means that serve to convey certain information in the process of dialogue can be classified as follows:

1. Visual aids:

- kinesics - hand, head, foot, body movements, stepping;
- facial expression (mimicry), eye expression (gaze);
- figure, holding the head;
- direction of gaze, visual communication;
- skin reactions - redness, paleness, sweating;
- proxemics (time and space of communication) - distance with the interlocutor, distance angle, personal latitudes;
- additional means of communication - exaggerating or hiding physical characteristics (gender, age, race); changing the natural body structure (clothing, hairstyle, cosmetics, glasses, jewelry, tattoos, mustache and beard, small items in the hand).

Kinesics. First of all, gestures can be included. There are three types of gestures, the first of which are considered adaptive and are used to reduce anxiety and restlessness, such as waving a pen. The second is symbols (emblems) that signify special consent to information. For example, giving a thumbs up to mean "OK" means "great, good". The last type is illustrators (this is the most common type of gesture and is used to illustrate an accompanying non-verbal message, for example: using a hand gesture to indicate the size or shape of an object. Head movement and position is to shake the head back and forth to indicate "no."

... Ra'no looked away again and dried his eyes. Anvar poured tea into a cup and handed it to Rana:

- Oh, Ra'no, drink.

Ra'no shook her head as if saying that she would not drink. Anvar took the tea quickly.

- Even if you don't drink it all, take a couple of sips (A. Qadiri, "Mehrobdan chayan").

There is also posture, and there are four common human positions: sitting, standing, stretching, and lying down.

Next is eye contact, which means that the face and eyes are the main focus during communication and together with ears and eyes make up most of the communication.

The last is a facial expression that shows the state of the communicator when he is tired, excited, angry, confused, disappointed, sad, confident, shy or bored.

Skin reactions can also provide information about the mental and physical state of the communicants during the dialogue. For example, in the following dialogue, the color change (redness) of the addressee's face represents his inner state (embarrassment):

...Ra'no did not understand Anvar's serious question:

- The sun must have made it red.

- You are wrong, Ra'no, - said Anvar, - I know the secret of the reddening of this flower, you are the reason for its reddening, your crimson lips...

"Don't joke," said Ra'no, blushing like a flower.

- Stop saying that, Ra'no, if you don't believe me, look in the mirror, is there a difference between your lips and the color of this red rose? (A. Qadiri, "Scorpion from the Altar").

In conclusion, in dialogic speech, non-verbal means accompanying and replacing linguistic means, giving emotionality to communication, are also used. As we mentioned, a

person conveys his thoughts or goals to another person through words and non-verbal units, exchange ideas, communicate, express mood. Dialogic speech is a clear example of this. Exchange of ideas, communication is a type of information exchange of dialogue.

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